

Analysis of the Anisotropic Term in the Implicit Algebraic Heat Flux Model in the Case of Low Prandtl Flow in Planar Impinging Jet Case

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doi.org/10.13182/NURETH20-40356

ABSTRACT

Numerical simulations of complex or industrial flows are predominantly simulated with Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations. In heat transfer problems, the additional term — the turbulent heat flux — needs to be modelled to be able to solve the average temperature equation. The simple gradient diffusion hypothesis can be used to estimate the turbulent heat flux from the average temperature gradient. However, in recent years, an implicit algebraic heat flux model (AHFM) has seen an increased use in the literature in connection with low Prandtl fluids. The AHFM can account for anisotropy of the turbulence properties, however, the inclusion of the anisotropy is usually avoided due to the instability it introduces. In this paper, we analyze the instability on a planar impinging jet case, combined with a more theoretical approach. We show that in certain regions, the anisotropic term can cause the turbulent heat flux to point in the opposite direction as the molecular heat flux, which inhibits the heat transfer. With certain values of parameters, the anisotropy term can even cause the turbulent heat flux to overpower the molecular heat flux and leads to conditions in which heat would be “conducted” (combination of molecular and turbulent heat flux) from cool regions to hot regions. We present inequalities that limit the model parameters for which the model with the anisotropic term is stable in a generic case. We also apply these limits to the forced convection case of the planar impinging jet and compare the limits to the identified numerical constraint.

KEYWORDS

RANS, low Prandtl number, AHFM, planar impinging jet

1. INTRODUCTION

An important role in the future of nuclear energy production is attributed to liquid metal cooled reactors. They are considered as coolants in GEN-IV reactor designs due to their beneficial properties in regards to cooling, as well as production of nuclear waste. One of the defining features of liquid metals is the high thermal diffusivity, relative to the kinematic viscosity. The small Prandtl number is the cause for a much larger thermal boundary layer, compared to the momentum boundary layer. The thermal turbulence models

used with modelling approaches, which make satisfactory predictions with unity Prandtl numbers, are lacking when applied to low-Prandtl fluids. In the recent years a few additional models were proposed and developed to address this gap at low Prandtl numbers.

The most common approach to simulating industrial flows is using the Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations. When simulating heat transfer problems in incompressible flows, the temperature equation gets the form

$$\frac{D(\rho c_p T)}{Dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} - \rho c_p \overline{\theta u_j} \right), \quad (1)$$

where T is the average temperature, κ is the thermal conductivity, and u_j the fluctuating part of velocity component (with U_j being the average velocity component) and θ the fluctuating part of temperature. The term $\overline{\theta u_j}$ is named the turbulent heat flux and to determine it, a model is required. A very popular choice among numericists for closing this term is the simple gradient diffusion hypothesis (SGDH), which assumes the turbulent heat flux is parallel and opposite to the average of temperature gradient and introduces one modelling parameter, the turbulent Prandtl number, Pr_t :

$$\overline{\theta u_j} = -\frac{\nu_t}{Pr_t} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j}, \quad (2)$$

where ν_t is the turbulence eddy viscosity and is calculated from the momentum turbulence variables.

As shown by Shams et al. [1], the SGDH underperforms for flows of low-Prandtl fluids. This is of importance with heat transfer in the liquid metal cooled reactors, since all the liquid metals considered for cooling have low Prandtl number. In addition, the SGDH proves to be inadequate in applications involving buoyancy [2,3]. The Algebraic Flux Models (AFM) were developed to address these deficiencies [4,5]. The AHFM introduces an algebraic relation for the turbulent heat flux:

$$\overline{\theta u_j} = -C_{t0} \frac{k}{\varepsilon} \left(C_{t1} \overline{u_i u_j} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + C_{t2} \overline{\theta u_j} \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_j} + C_{t3} \beta g_i \overline{\theta^2} \right) + C_{t4} a_{ij} \overline{\theta u_j}. \quad (3)$$

Here, k and ε are the turbulence kinetic energy and its dissipation rate, respectively. a_{ij} is the Reynolds stress anisotropy tensor given as $a_{ij} = \frac{\overline{u_i u_j}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij}$ and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta symbol. C_{t_i} for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 4$ are the model constants. The model introduces the temperature variance, $\overline{\theta^2}$, for which an additional transport equation is solved

$$\frac{D(\rho \overline{\theta^2})}{Dt} = -2\rho \overline{\theta u_i} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} - \rho \frac{\overline{\theta^2} k}{R \varepsilon} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(\frac{\kappa}{c_p} + \frac{\rho \nu_t}{Pr_t} \right) \frac{\partial \overline{\theta^2}}{\partial x_i} \right]. \quad (4)$$

R is the ratio between the thermal and mechanical time-scales and is an additional model parameter. The derivation of the AHFM can be found in [6].

The focus of the present paper, however, is not the behaviour of the buoyant term, but rather the behaviour of the anisotropy term connected with the model parameter C_{t4} . In the literature, there are different values, or even correlations, recommended for the values of C_{t_i} parameters. The recommendations take into account the flow regimes. Since the case we were applying the AHFM model to is in forced convection regime, we decided to use the AHFM-NRG version of the model. The details of the particular version are described by Shams et al. in [7]. The model introduces a correlation for the parameter C_{t1} that dramatically reduces the error in forced convection cases:

$$C_{t1} = \begin{cases} 0.053 \ln(RePr) - 0.27 & \text{if } RePr > 180 \\ 0.25 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (5)$$

The values of the other model parameters we used are given in the Table I. The parameter in Table I that differs from the value given in [7], is the value of C_{t_4} parameter which we adapted to 1.5 to investigate the behaviour of the model. Usually, the value of C_{t_4} is set to 0 and the instability with the term is therefore not noticed.

Table I. Values of AHFM coefficients used in this study.

C_{t_0}	C_{t_1}	C_{t_2}	C_{t_3}	C_{t_4}
0.15	Eq. 5	0.6	2.5	1.5

In Section 2 we briefly describe the case that was used to investigate the AHFM. With Section 3 we introduce the problem that we identified and in Section 4 we identify and propose limits for the values of C_{t_4} that prevent the instability of occurring.

2. CASE DESCRIPTION

Figure 1. Sketch of geometry in the reference DNS [8] case used to study the behaviour of the anisotropic term of the AHFM model.

In this paper we present the details of investigation into the behaviour of the anisotropic term of the AHFM. For this purpose we investigated the behaviour of the model on a planar impinging jet of Duponcheel and Bartosiewicz [8]. As shown in Fig. 1, the domain is comprised of two parts. A smaller channel of width B is used to obtain a fully developed inflow boundary condition for the side of a channel of width H . The latter channel has two outflows on the sides. In the third direction (along the z axis), a periodic boundary condition is used, making the average flow two-dimensional. The DNS contains data for two Reynolds numbers (based on the width of inflow): 4000 and 5700. For the purposes of our investigation we only compared the case with the higher Reynolds number of 5700, which also has more turbulence anisotropy. Although the study is aimed at the low Prandtl numbers, for testing purposes we used the unity Prandtl number, since the encountered problem affects all Prandtl numbers, but is more pronounced at higher Prandtl numbers since the temperature gradients are in general, higher.

Recent comparison of RANS simulations of the impinging jet and the performance of the AHFM model without the anisotropic term, can be found in the paper by De Santis et. al [9]. This impinging jet case is chosen, since it shows significant anisotropy of turbulence in the region where the jet hits the wall.

The geometry of the case follows the set-up of the DNS and is the same as in the paper by De Santis et. al [9]. The domain in the RANS calculation is two-dimensional and reduced, since no significant difference to the full DNS domain was observed. The RANS simulation domain has the size L equal to $40B$ and height H equal to $2B$. Results from channel flow simulation are used as the velocity inflow boundary condition for velocity and turbulence inlet profiles. The temperature of the fluid at the inlet is set to 2 and the temperature of the walls is set to 1.

Approximately 150 thousand cells were used for the simulation. The grid sensitivity study was performed at a lower Reynolds number and can be found in [9]. The grid in the reference was chosen conservatively and we believe it is applicable to this case. Nevertheless the aim of this paper is to investigate the instability of the model, which as we show, is generally independent from the quality of the mesh.

We performed our investigations with three momentum turbulence models: the Launder-Sharma $k-\varepsilon$ [10], $k-\omega$ SST [11], and the $v2-f$ model [12, 13]. While the results and observations depend on the exact model used, the general trends are similar for all three models used. All the simulations were produced with OpenFOAM v8 with an in-house implementation of the AHFM model.

3. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

To predict the turbulent heat flux $\overline{\theta u_j}$ from Eq. (3), the equations are rewritten into the matrix form

$$M_{ij}\overline{\theta u_j} = b_i, \quad (6)$$

where

$$M_{ij} = \delta_{ij} + C_{t_0}C_{t_2}\frac{k}{\epsilon}\frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} - C_{t_4}a_{ij} \quad (7)$$

and

$$b_i = -C_{t_0}\frac{k}{\epsilon}\left(C_{t_1}\overline{u_i u_j}\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial x_j} + C_{t_3}\beta\overline{\theta^2}g_i\right). \quad (8)$$

This system is solved in each cell by using a direct inversion by calculating the known inverse of 3×3 sized matrices.

Figure 2. Color map of the determinant of matrix M obtained with Launder-Sharma $k-\varepsilon$ momentum turbulence model and value of $C_{t_4} = 1.5$.

Figure 3. Average temperature field obtained with Launder-Sharma $k-\epsilon$ momentum turbulence model and value of $C_{t_4} = 1.5$.

From the above matrix formula a problem can already be observed connected with the anisotropic term (term with the C_{t_4} coefficient). Under appropriate circumstances, the term can cause the matrix M to become ill conditioned or singular. Fig. 2 shows the determinant of the matrix M in the planar impinging jet case for the value of $C_{t_4} = 1.5$. Consequently, the temperature solution obtained has visible instabilities in the jet impingement region, as seen in Fig. 3. The instability is limited to the lower part of the region, because its manifestation is also connected to the right side hand of Eq. (6). Since in the forced convection case b_i is only connected to the temperature gradient, and the temperature gradient is 0 in the core of the jet, the turbulent heat flux is unaffected by the matrix becoming ill-conditioned.

Figure 4. Magnitude of first (left) and second (right) eigenvalue of matrix M through the domain. Obtained with the Launder-Sharma $k-\epsilon$ model and $C_{t_4} = 1.5$.

Since the matrix M is not symmetric, its eigenvalues are complex. In this case, they are mostly real but remain complex in a limited area. This is why in Fig. 4 the magnitude of eigenvalues are shown. The value of the third eigenvalue is 1 in the whole domain, since the case is two-dimensional. As seen in the Fig. 4, only the magnitude of one eigenvalue approaches the value 0.

It is useful to note that while singularity of the matrix is problematic for the calculation, it is not the only issue arising with connection of negative determinant of matrix M . Leaving the rigorous mathematical derivation at the side, the issue is perhaps best demonstrated with a simplified example. What follows is a demonstration of physical consequences of a negative determinant of matrix M .

In the cases where gravity is absent, the turbulent heat flux is then simply the rotated gradient of the average temperature gradient

$$\overline{\theta u_j} = -C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} (M^{-1})_{ji} \overline{u_i u_k} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_k}. \quad (9)$$

Since the matrix M does contain the term proportional to $-\overline{u_i u_j}$, let us, for the sake of demonstration, assume that we have a limited region in which the matrix M is approximately equal to the negative Reynolds stress $M_{ij} \sim -\overline{u_i u_j}$. The determinant of such matrix M is negative, since the determinant of the Reynolds stress tensor is always non-negative [14]. In such assumed case and in a limited region, the turbulent heat flux

would be equal to

$$\overline{\theta u_j} \sim C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_k}. \quad (10)$$

That is, the turbulent heat flux would be parallel and point in the opposite direction of the molecular heat flux. Since the model constants C_{t_0} and C_{t_2} are arbitrary, it can be scaled arbitrarily. The turbulent heat flux can therefore be set up to overpower the molecular heat flux in the temperature equation 1 and would cause the total heat flux to transport heat from cold regions to hot regions. This may be a violation of the second law of thermodynamics, however, we cannot show this directly since we must observe that this consequence arose due to macroscopic motion of the fluid, which we averaged over when deducing the RANS equations.

Nevertheless, the mathematical consequences of such configuration for Eq. (1) are clear. In the limited region, Eq. (1) becomes an inverse parabolic partial differential equation, which is ill conditioned. While it might be possible that such an ill conditioned configuration would exist locally (where the average motion of fluid would advect the heat away from a region in which the combination of turbulent and molecular heat flux would transfer heat from cold regions to hot regions), in the general applications, turbulence usually enhances the molecular heat flux and does not inhibit or reverse it.

Although we could not find any cases where the determinant of matrix M would be negative we do not claim that such cases do not exist. Nevertheless, it is clear that the mathematical construction of the AHFM model cannot handle any configurations where the determinant of matrix M becomes 0.

4. LIMITS ON MODEL PARAMETERS

Figure 5. Local values for parameter C_{t_4} that ensure $\det(M) > 0$ with Launder-Sharma $k-\varepsilon$ model and standard values for other parameters.

The first approach that comes to mind with the above described problem is to limit the parameter C_{t_4} to values, which prevent the matrix M of becoming singular. Note that the matrix M does not depend on any thermal variables. It only depends on momentum field properties like Reynolds stresses, turbulence dissipation rate and derivatives of average velocity. For a forced convection case, where fields associated with the momentum field are decoupled from the temperature, this allows to set the limits for parameter C_{t_4} based solely on the calculation of the momentum field.

Fig. 5 shows the value of C_{t_4} needs to be adapted in different regions so as to ensure that $\det(M) > 0$. This is obtained with Launder-Sharma $k-\varepsilon$ model and values for other parameters as given in Table I.

Figure 6. Limits for model parameters C_{t_4} and the product $C_{t_0}C_{t_2}$ that ensure $\det(M) > 0$ on a planar impinging jet case. The lower left corner contains the region for which no instability is encountered.

Since the matrix M depends also on parameters C_{t_0} and C_{t_2} , this reflects in the maximal value of C_{t_4} that can be used. However, note that the dependence is only on the product of these two parameters. Since it also depends on the momentum variables the result also varies with the momentum turbulence model applied. Fig. 6 shows the result of this investigation and provides limits for model parameters. If the values of C_{t_4} and the product $C_{t_0}C_{t_2}$ are chosen to the left and below the curve for individual turbulence model, the matrix M will not become singular. We note here that even with the value $C_{t_4} = 0$, the model can still become unstable if sufficiently high values of the product $C_{t_0}C_{t_2}$ are used.

4.1. Case independent constrains

While the determination of C_{t_4} for a particular test case with different momentum turbulence models can be interesting, it lacks components that help us understand the sources of these constraints and how they are influenced by different momentum turbulence models.

Through an application of the Gershgorin's circle theorem [15], we provide inequalities that are less precise than the criterion with the determinant, however, they allow for more insight and are easier to implement in a computational code. We first develop the inequalities for a two dimensional case. The matrix M in such a case has one eigenvalue that is equal to one and thus positive. Hence, in order to have a positive determinant with the two other eigenvalues, 3 possibilities exist for matrix M : either the two other eigenvalues are negative, are positive, or are a complex conjugate pair. Since negative eigenvalues could imply reversal of the turbulent heat flux, as well as due to the apparent spatial continuity of eigenvalues in the region where one becomes negative, we focus on conditions to ensure all three eigenvalues are positive. Note that the discontinuity of eigenvalues at the inflow corresponds to the discontinuity of the boundary condition.

The Gershgorin circle theorem is a theorem that binds the spectrum of a square matrix. The details of the application of it and derivation of the two criteria are given in the Appendix A. Two necessary and two sufficient conditions are developed:

- Necessary:

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \left| \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right| \geq C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} - \frac{|\overline{u_i u_j}|}{k} \right). \quad (11)$$

- Sufficient:

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} - C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \left| \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right| \geq C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} + \frac{|\overline{u_i u_j}|}{k} \right). \quad (12)$$

Note that in each condition above no Einstein summation convention is implied. Rather, there are two combinations: $(i, j) = (x, y)$ or $(i, j) = (y, x)$. In the following text we refer to the first possibility as the condition in the x direction and the second possibility as condition in the y direction. Only combination of both possibilities leads to a full necessary or sufficient condition on the determinant of matrix M . As noted in the Appendix A the sufficient condition can lead to conjugate eigenvalues with positive real part. That is, eigenvalues that are below and above the positive real axis \mathbb{R}_+ . A condition to have strictly real positive eigenvalues (that is, on the positive real axis \mathbb{R}_+ itself) could be developed with a criterion suggested in Appendix A but no apparent need has been determined. Note also, that if C_{t_4} is chosen in order to respect the sufficient condition, then it respects the necessary condition as well. The conditions are therefore well-defined, and we will focus only on the sufficient condition below.

As can be seen from the derived conditions, the model parameters are only constrained with the values of the momentum field. The temperature and turbulent heat flow themselves are not involved in the determination of the limits.

4.1.1. Application of case independent constrains

Figure 7. Sufficient conditions on C_{t_4} for directions x and y for different momentum turbulence models in the planar impinging jet case.

Fig. 7 shows the sufficient condition expressed in Eq. (12) in x and y directions for the Launder-Sharma k- ϵ and k- ω SST turbulence model. It illustrates that both conditions are required to conclude on the maximum value of C_{t_4} . Indeed, some cells do not require a maximum value on C_{t_4} below 1.5 for the x -condition, however they do for the y -condition and vice-versa. Also note the difference from Fig. 5. While the condition

on the determinant is more precise and limited to the triangular shape only, the sufficient condition is stricter and the regions outside the triangular shape could also limit the maximal value of C_{t4} .

Figure 8. Sufficient condition 12 applied to the planar impinging jet case. Different colors mark the different momentum turbulence models. Both directions are shown for each turbulence model with the dashed-dotted line marking the intersection.

Similar to the determinant criterion, we can find the maximal value of C_{t4} in the whole domain for both criteria. Fig. 8 illustrates the sufficient condition on C_{t4} value for different momentum turbulence models in the impinging jet case. As shown in Fig. 8, the final C_{t4} value is obtained as the most restricted condition provided by two equations for each model.

Figure 9. Comparison of limits obtained with the Geshgorin circle theorem and with the determinant method for different momentum turbulence models.

In Fig. 9 we compare the sufficient condition obtained by the Gershgorin method with the exact condition obtained by the determinant criterion. As expected, the Gershgorin method ends up with a bound consistent with that obtained with the determinant method. Although the condition provided is easier to handle, it is

more restrictive because in the method using the Gershgorin theorem, the disks are assumed to not intersect the left side of the complex plane, whereas in reality this is not a necessary condition to provide positive eigenvalues.

The proposed method based on the Gershgorin circle theorem can be expanded to three dimensional cases and the derivation can be found in Appendix B.

Figure 10. Temperature field obtained with $C_{t_4} = 0.4$ with Launder-Sharma $k-\varepsilon$ model.

Figure 11. Temperature profiles with different values for C_{t_4} .

For completeness, in Fig. 10 we present the temperature field obtained with a value of coefficient $C_{t_4} = 0.4$, which is below the value of ≈ 0.5 , at which with the Launder-Sharma $k-\varepsilon$ model the AHFM becomes unstable. Fig. 11 shows comparison on the profile lines given in the DNS. Note that the centerline of the jet is missing. The problematic zone is entirely contained within $\frac{|x|}{B} < 1$. The issues and the differences are therefore not exhibited so dramatically.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we demonstrate that the anisotropic term of the AHFM can cause the algebraic system of equations for calculation of turbulent heat flux to become ill conditioned and singular. While the problem we were investigating originated as a numerical problem, we indicate that it has the potential to cancel or reverse the total heat flux in the temperature equation and lead to an unstable and potentially non-physical configuration. While it is unclear to us, which configurations of molecular and turbulent heat fluxes are impossible from the physical point of view, we propose limiting the model in a way that prevents numerical problems.

For this purpose we employed the Gershgorin circle theorem to find the necessary and sufficient conditions

that the coefficients of the model have to satisfy. The conditions depend only on the fields of the momentum turbulence. So in a case, where DNS data is available, the limits for the coefficients can be estimated before the simulation undertaken, although the exact values will depend on the momentum turbulence model employed. In forced convection cases where the momentum fields are decoupled from the thermal fields limitations of the parameters can be determined after momentum field has been simulated. The natural convection cases, however, require more care. While this problem can be present in the natural convection cases, since the momentum and temperature fields are coupled, no such analysis can be performed.

A possible future expansion and investigation of the conditions would be to include conjugate eigenvalues that still allow for the determinant of matrix to remain positive. However, we would first need to find a case where such eigenvalues could be found.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2019–2020 under grant agreement No. 945077 (PATRICIA project).

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Figure 12. Illustration of the Gershgorin disks theorem.

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A. DERIVATION OF INEQUALITIES FOR A 2D CASE

Reminder of the theorem

The Gershgorin circle theorem binds the eigenvalues to the diagonal values of a square matrix. It was published by Gershgorin in 1931 [15]. Let A be a complex $n \times n$ matrix:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} & & \\ & a_{i,j} & \\ & & \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{M}_n(\mathbb{C})$$

Let r_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be the sum of the absolute values of the non-diagonal entries in the i -th row:

$$r_i = \sum_{j \neq i} |a_{ij}|. \quad (13)$$

Let $D(a_{ii}, r_i) \subset \mathbb{C}$ be a closed disc, called a Gershgorin disc, centered at a_{ii} with a radius r_i . See Fig. 12 for an illustration.

The Gershgorin theorem states that every eigenvalue of matrix A is contained at least within one such disc. If the disc is disjunct the eigenvalue must be contained within it, however, if the disc intersect another disc, it is possible that it contains no eigenvalue and the intersecting disc contains both.

Conditions to have positive eigenvalues

As described in the text above, we chose to have a positive determinant of matrix M by demanding that all three eigenvalues are positive. In this way we intend to limit the possible values of the model parameter C_{t4} . Since it is a two dimensional case, M has zero values on its 3rd row and column except on its diagonal. Moreover, this last diagonal term is positive and around 1. So that, the other eigenvalues of M are the ones from the submatrix composed of the 2 first rows and columns of M . Note that since M is a real matrix, all discs are centered on the real axis \mathbb{R} .

Figure 13. Necessary condition for a real matrix.

The necessary condition can be derived by demanding, that each Gershgorin disc intersects the positive real axis \mathbb{R}_+ as shown in Fig. 13. This requirement can be separated in two cases:

- If $a_{ii} \leq 0$, then we require $|a_{ii}| < r_i$, which implies $-a_{ii} < r_i$.
- If $a_{ii} > 0$, some part of the \mathbb{R}_+ is already contained in the disc.

Since r_i is positive, both cases can be summarized into the condition

$$a_{ii} + r_i > 0, \quad (14)$$

for $i = 1, 2$.

If we insert the appropriate terms for matrix M , we can write

$$1 + C_{t0}C_{t2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} - C_{t4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} \right) + \left| C_{t0}C_{t2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} - C_{t4} \frac{\overline{u_i u_j}}{k} \right| > 0. \quad (15)$$

By using the triangle inequality and the positivity of model parameters, a stricter necessary inequality (however, not sufficient condition) can be written down, since the following condition is required for the

previous condition to be met.

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \left| \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right| > C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} - \frac{|\overline{u_i u_j}|}{k} \right), \quad (16)$$

for $i = 1, 2$, or, for both directions x and y .

A possible sufficient condition is to prevent any of the Gershgorin discs to intersect the negative real axis \mathbb{R}_- . This condition can be written as $a_{ii} - r_i > 0$. Written with the appropriate terms of matrix M this conditions is

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} - C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} \right) - \left| C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} - C_{t_4} \frac{\overline{u_i u_j}}{k} \right| > 0. \quad (17)$$

By applying the triangle inequality and the positivity of model parameters, a stricter inequality can be written down, since the following condition is required for the previous condition to be met.

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} - C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \left| \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right| > C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2}}{k} - \frac{2}{3} + \frac{|\overline{u_i u_j}|}{k} \right) \quad (18)$$

for $i = 1, 2$, or, for both directions x and y .

B. EXTENSION TO 3D CASES

Previous inequalities can be extend to 3D case by following the same reasoning. This results in the following inequalities:

- for the necessary condition

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} + \left| \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right| + \left| \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_i} \right| \right) > C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2} - |\overline{u_i u_j}| - |\overline{u_i u_k}|}{k} - \frac{2}{3} \right) \quad (19)$$

- and for the sufficient condition

$$1 + C_{t_0} C_{t_2} \frac{k}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} - \left| \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right| - \left| \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_i} \right| \right) > C_{t_4} \left(\frac{\overline{u_i^2} + |\overline{u_i u_j}| + |\overline{u_i u_k}|}{k} - \frac{2}{3} \right). \quad (20)$$

i, j, k denote different subscripts without summation. That way, since j and k have symmetric roles, 3 inequalities must be satisfied from each generic inequality.